

Original Research Article

Formulated Sorghum Media for Cultivation of *Escherichia coli* (NCTC10418) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (NCTC 6750)

Izebe KS^{1*}, Ya'aba Y¹, Onaolapo JA², Ibrahim K¹, Ibrahim YKE², Oladosu P¹, Njoku M¹,
Mohammed SB¹, Ezeunala M¹ and Olurinola PF²

Abstract

¹Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development, Idu, Abuja, Nigeria

²Department of Pharmaceutical Microbiology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

* Corresponding Author's E-mail: alkysim@yahoo.com
Mob.: +234 8054492351

The study was aimed to formulate sorghum based media for the cultivation of *E.coli* and *P.aeruginosa*. The sorghum grains were treated of debris, soaked in distilled water and ground into paste. The fibers removed and centrifuged at 9000 rpm for 15 minutes. The protein-like and starch deposited were dried. The glucan and starch were digested with pepsin and amylase enzymes to protein and sugar digest followed by combinations and the pH adjusted to 7.2 and sterilized to obtained sorghum media. sorghum and Nutrient broth were inoculated with diluted 24 hours. of *E.coli* and *P.aeruginosa*. The growth of these bacteria were visualized, absorbance (OD) and viable count estimated. A growth profile of *E.coli* and *P.aeruginosa* in Nutrient and sorghum media were monitored using spectrophotometric for six hours. The OD 0.8 for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* in Sorghum media while OD 1.0 and 0.9 for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* in Nutrient Broth. The mean viable count of *E.coli* was $5.6 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.01$ and $4.9 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.004$ CFU/mL in Nutrient and sorghum media. While *P. aeruginosa* mean viable count was $5.1 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.011$ and $4.0 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.005$ CFU/mL in Nutrient and sorghum media respectively with no growth. The growth curve pattern of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* showed no lag phase and lengthen log phase. The findings of this study showed that developed Sorghum media can promote the growth of bacteria in the samewayas the Nutrient broth.

Keywords: Absorbance, *E.coli*, Enzymatic digestion, Growth curve, *P.aeruginosa*. Sorghum grains, Sorghum media, Turbidity, Viable count, Nutrient broth

INTRODUCTION

Culture media are bedrock of identification and manipulation of bacteria and fungi in all sphere of laboratory with regards to cultivation. A microbiological culture medium is a substance that encourages the growth, support, and survival of microorganisms. Culture media contains nutrients, growth promoting factors, energy sources, buffer salts, minerals, metals, and gelling agents (Gerard *et al.*, 2018). Culture media should contain the basic requirements that would promote growth of microorganisms. The protein, carbon, and mineral sources are parts of requirement for promoting

growth. There are variations in growth requirement of microorganisms in different environment such as nutrients, pH, osmotic conditions and temperature (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2002). Sandle and Tidswell (2010), emphasized needs for high quality media to achieve accurate, reproducible and repeated microbiological test results. The two common general medium types are nutrient agar or broth, and tryptone soya agar or broth. The manufacturing of media is done either in-house (whereby a dehydrated formulation is used) or, more commonly, is purchased ready made (Sandle, 2003).

There has high cost of readymade media (Adesemoye and Adedire, 2005). The quality of readymade media or dehydrated or powder media is uncertain as a result to delayed clearance and final destiny to the market. Other researchers have source for cheap materials towards formulation of media for the growth of bacteria and fungi (Deivanayaki and Iruthayaraj, 2012; Ravathie *et al.*, 2012; Vasantha Raj *et al.*, 2013; Basu *et al.*, 2015; Pratibha *et al.*, 2018). Sorghum (*Family Andropogaceae*) is the fourth most important cereal crop in the world surpassed only by rice, wheat and maize respectively. In Nigeria, sorghum is staple food for most of the households. Sorghum is grown in most of the States of Nigeria and large quantity harvested annually. This study is aimed at development through the formulation of sorghum grains into culture media for the cultivation of *E.coli* and *P.aeruginosa* a research bacterial tools in the laboratory.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sorghum grains of short kaura variety (SK 5912) was obtained and identified by Institute of Agricultural Research, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria. Two thousand grams (2000 g) of sorghum grains were cleaned up by removing debris and stones and soaked in distilled water for 24 hours. After 24 hours, the soaked grains were ground with miller machine to paste. The sorghum mixture was centrifuged at 9,000 rotations per minutes (rpm) for 10 minutes and the protein-like material appeared brownish and in the upper layer, while the starchy material in the bottom layer. The protein-like material was scrapped with cleaned spatula and separated from the starchy materials. These materials were dried 25°C for three days and stored at 4°C in refrigerator until requested for use for digestion of protein and carbohydrate

Sorghum starch digestion

Twenty grams (20g) of starch was dissolved in 1.0 L flask and placed in water-bath with shaker maintained at 70 °C and 15.0 mL of *Hitempase* was added for one hour. and cooled to 60°C for 3.0 mL of *Glycoamylase* another 30 minutes and the mixture allowed to cool followed by centrifuge 4500 rpm. The filtrate constituted the sugar/starch digest. The sugar content was estimated with oxidase method (Basak, 2007).

Sorghum protein material digestion

Twenty grams (20g) of the protein material (glycan) was dispensed into 1.0 L in flask and placed in water-bath with shaker maintained at 52°C and pepsin solution

(*Pepsin* 1.0g, 6.0mL HCL) for 4 hours.(Cruickshank *et al.*,1983).The total protein estimation was carried out using with Biuret method (Fenk *et al.*, 2007).

Media composition

The media composition was based on addition of sorghum starch digest to sorghum protein digest in the ratio of 50mL to 950 mL shown in the table below (Table 1).

The reconstituted broth was each subjected to pH 7.4 and filtered in Whatman filter paper. The filtrates were dispensed into flasks and bottles and sterilized at 121°C for 15 minutes.

Inoculation with *E. coli* and *P.aeruginosa*

The test bacteria of *E.coli* (NCTC 10418) and *P.aeruginosa* (NCTC 6750) were obtained the Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development Idu, Abuja, Nigeria. The 24 hours cultures of *E.coli* and *P. aeruginosa*, 0.2 ml of each was used to inoculate labelled formulated Sorghum media and prepared labelled dehydrated Nutrient broth (Oxoid) capped 15 mL test tubes in triplicates and with control tubes without test bacteria and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Visual observation

All the inoculated tubes were observed for visual growth by comparing with controls for turbidity of sorghum and Nutrient media at the end of 24 hours.

Spectrophotometric readings of 24 hours cultures of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*

The Spectronic 20 was switched on for 15 minutes and the absorbance (OD) was adjusted to 540 nm. The blanks used include sorghum and Nutrient media without test bacteria. The 24 hours, cultures of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* were each read against the blank.

Viable count

Dilutions of 1:10 were made on the overnight cultures of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* in Nutrient and formulated sorghum media to obtained 10¹⁸ and 1.0 mL each was aseptically dispensed to sterile Tryptic Soya Agar Petri dishes in triplicate. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The colonies on the Tryptic Soya Agar plates

Table 1. Combination of sugar and protein digest in the formulation of sorghum broth

Sugar (mL)	Digest	50	100	150	200	250	300	400
Protein (mL)	Digest	950	900	850	800	750	700	600

Table 2. Growth profile of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* in sorghum and hydrated nutrient broth

Growth profile	Sorghum media		Nutrient broth	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>
Visualize	++	++	++	++
Absorbance (540 nm)	0.790	0.8	1.00	0.9
Viable count CFU/mL	$4.9 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.01$	$4.0 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.005$	$5.6 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.004$	$5.1 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.011$

each for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* were counted as colony forming unit (CFU/mL) using colony coulter.

Determination of growth curves

The Bio-screen (Bio-screen C (200 wells), Biolink Laboratories, Finland) was put on to booth. The sterile micro-wells were each dispensed with 0.3mL of formulated sorghum broth in the honey wells. Similarly, 0.3mL of sterile Nutrient broth was dispensed into the labeled honey wells. 0.05mL of 3 hours culture of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* was each inoculated the labeled wells of sorghum and dehydrated Nutrient broth. The inoculated wells were transferred into chamber and the absorbance at 540 nm adjusted time (hours) interval of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 hours.

Statistical Analysis

The data generated were subjected to SPSS (version 20) statistical software. The data generated were subjected to standard mean of deviations calculations and presented in graphical and tabular forms.

RESULTS

The formulated sorghum broth (Table 1) combination were sterilized and inoculated with *E. coli* (NCTC 1041) and *P. aeruginosa* (NCTC 6750). The dehydrated Nutrient broth (Oxoid) was also sterilized and inoculated with *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. The growths at 24 hour in these media showed turbidity (Table 2) and when read on spectrophotometer at 540 nm gave varied readings. The absorbance (OD) ranged from 0.79 to 1.0 with Nutrient broth having higher than formulated sorghum broth. Similarly, the viable counts for the formulated sorghum

broth and Nutrient broth gave mean CFU/mL from $4.9 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.01$ to $5.6 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.004$ CFU/mL (Table 2). The mean viable count of *E. coli* in sorghum media was $4.9 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.01$ CFU/mL and $5.6 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.004$ CFU/mL in Nutrient broth. The mean viable count of *P. aeruginosa* was $4.0 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.005$ CFU/mL and $5.1 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.011$ CFU/mL in sorghum and Nutrient media respectively.

The growth profiles of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* in formulated sorghum media and Nutrient broth (Figure 1 and 2) gave growth curves. The growth profile of *E. coli* in formulated sorghum broth and Nutrient broth was found to be similar. The growth curve of *P. aeruginosa* in these media showed rapid growth in Nutrient broth than formulated Sorghum media. The formulated sorghum broth and hydrated nutrient broth on the growth pattern showed similarity with minute difference as shown in table 2.

DISCUSSION

The bases for the identification of microorganisms in the laboratory are the ability to cultivate these microorganisms for identifications and other microbiological work. The dehydrated or commercially produced culture media are imported especially in underdeveloped countries which unavoidably add to financial constrain on the economy. According to Adesemoye and Adedire (2005), reported higher cost of culture media that warrant the formulation of media. The formulated sorghum media promoted the growth of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* after 24 hours, incubation with high turbidity when viewed visually and with spectrophotometric gave high absorbance when compared with Nutrient broth. The mean viable count for *E. coli* was found to be $5.6 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.004$ CFU/mL for Nutrient broth while in formulated sorghum media the mean viable count was $3.0 \times 10^{20} \pm 0.011$ CFU/mL. The mean viable count of *P. aeruginosa* was $5.1 \times 10^{22} \pm 0.011$ and $4.0 \times 10^{20} \pm 0.005$ CFU/mL in Nutrient broth

Figure 1. Growth profile of *E. coli* in Nutrient (A) and formulated sorghum media (B)

Figure 2. Growth profile of *P. aeruginosa* in Nutrient (A) and formulated sorghum media (B)

and formulated Sorghum media respectively. The growth curves (Figure 1 and 2) of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* in sorghum and Nutrient media gave a similar pattern of growth with no lag phase based on fact that the bacteria were grown for 3hrs before inoculated in the broth to continue into log phase which is ideal for susceptibility studies. The formulated sorghum broth promotes the growth of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* from the absorbance and viable count when compared to similar growth in Nutrient broth. The findings of this work showed that

growths of *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* in sorghum media formulations can be used as substitute to Nutrient broth as routine media for basal media for other preparations in dilutions and sugar inclusion for biochemical related tests in the identification of bacteria. In a similar study, Pratibha *et al.* (2018) reported formulations from seeds and peel extract supported growth of *E. coli*, *Serratiasp* and *P. aeruginosa*. SathiyaVimal *et al.* (2013) also reported formulations from Gooseberry and use carrot, tomato, cabbage and pumpkin was report by Deivanayaki

and Iruthayaraj (2012) to cultivate bacteria and fungi. Some researchers also used cow pea, green gram and black gram as starch and protein substitutes to grow bacteria and fungi (Wasas *et al.* (1999) in order to reduce cost of culture media. In the vein, Uthayasooryan *et al.* (2020) in similar work reported alternative formulated media to convectional Nutrient broth using local cheap material to cultivate bacteria and fungi.

CONCLUSION

The formulation of sorghum broth has shown to compared favorably in the presence of high turbid growth, absorbance values and growth curves profile with dehydrated Nutrient broth in cultivation of bacteria such *E.coli* and *P.aeruginosa*. The sorghum media is an alternative culture media to Nutrient Broth as routine media. Sorghum media is sourced locally from cheap sorghum grains. The formulated sorghum media was found to contain 0.103 g sugars and 2.4 g proteins per litre to give 2.503 g /L when compared with Nutrient broth composition of 6.0 g of peptone, 3.0 g of yeast extract and 1.5 g beef extract to give 10.5 g per liter.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD), Idu- Abuja for the use of its facilities.

Conflict of Interest

There is no any conflict of interest declared by the authors.

REFERENCES

- Adesemoye AO, Adedire CO (2005). Use of Cereals as basal medium for the formulation of alternative culture media for fungi, *World J Microbiol. Biotech*, 21: 329-336.
- Basak A (2007). Development a rapid and inexpensive plasma glucose estimation by two-point kinetic method based on glucose oxidase-peroxidase enzymes. *India J. Clin. Biochem.* 22: 156-160.
- Basu S, Bose C, Ojha N, et al. (2015). Evolution of bacterial and fungal growth media. *Bioinformation*.11(4):182-184.
- Bhattacharya S, Vijayalakshmi N, Parija SC (2002). Uncultivable bacteria: Implications and recent trends towards identification. *Indian J Med Microbiol*: 20:174-7.
- Cruickshank R, Duguid JP, Marmion BP, Swain RHA (1983). *Medical Microbiology Vol 2*. Churchill Livingstone Publisher, Edinburgh, Scotland.96-147.
- Deivanayaki M, Iruthayaraj AP (2012). Alternative vegetable nutrient source for microbial growth, *Inter. J. Biosci*, 2: 47-51.
- Fenk CJ, Kaufman N, Gerbig DGJ (2007) *Chem. Educ.* 2007, 84, 1676-1678.
- Gerald JT, Berdell RF, Christine IC (2018). *Microbiology: An Introduction*. 11th Edition Pearson Publishers. India. Media Growth pp 159-167.
- Pratibha J, Mrunalini S, Arati K, Suraj P, Kirti D, Jaspal KO (2018). Formulation of Cost Effective Alternative Bacterial Culture Media Using Fruit and Vegetables Waste. *Int. J. Cur. Res. Rev.* 10(2): 1022-1037.
- Ravathie PS, R. Nirmala, N. Kularajany (2012). *J. Nat. Prod. Plant Res.* 2: 697-700.
- Sandle and E.C. Tidswell, EC (2010). (Editors). *Microbiology and Sterility Assurance in Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices*; New Delhi: Business Horizons, pp 101-120.
- Sandle T (2003). Selection and Use of Cleaning and Disinfection Agents in Pharmaceutical Manufacturing. In N. Hodges and G. Hanlon (Editors). *Industrial Pharmaceutical Microbiology Standards and Controls*; *Euromed Communications*, England (chapter revised on several occasions).
- Sandle T (2014). Assessment of Culture Media in Pharmaceutical Microbiology, PhD thesis.
- Uthayasooryan M, Sevvell P, Nirmala Rm, Sutharshiny S (2016). Formulation of alternative culture media for bacterial and fungal growth. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*, 8(1):431-436 (<http://scholarsresearchlibrary.com/archive.html>).
- Vasantha Raj SS, Senthilkumar RP, Jagannathan S (2013). Natural Sources of Gooseberry Component used for Microbial Culture Medium *J. Appl. Pharm. Sci.* 3(11): 040-044